

Synthesis and Reactions of Platinum(II) and Palladium(II) Chelates with 8-quinolinols[†]

P. UMAPATHY*, (Mrs.) S. CHANDRASEKHAR and K. D. GHUGE

National Chemical Laboratory, Poona-411 008

Manuscript received 7 July 1980, revised 27 October 1980, accepted 28 January 1981

Platinum(II) and palladium(II) chelates with 8-quinolinols of the type, ML_2 ($M=Pt$; $HL=8$ -quinolinol or 5,7-dichloro- or 5,7-dibromo- or 5,7-diiodo-8-quinolinol, $M=Pd$; $HL=5,7$ -dihalogeno-8-quinolinol) have been synthesized by the reaction of K_2PtCl_4 or Na_2PdCl_4 with the appropriate ligand. *Bis*(8-quinolinolato)platinum(II) or palladium(II) readily reacts with chlorine, bromine or iodine monochloride, ICl , etc. to yield the corresponding Pt(IV) or Pd(IV) complexes. The reaction with anhydrous $SnCl_2$ yielded Pt(II) or Pd(II) complexes containing bivalent tin. The ir, uv-visible data for the reaction products are presented and discussed. The ir spectral data indicate that the oxidative addition of the halogen has been to *trans*-positions in the complex.

THE oxidative addition reactions involving 4- and 5-coordinate complexes of transition metals with d^8 electron configuration, is a subject of considerable current interest¹⁻⁸. Many group VIII transition metal complexes of d^8 configuration are readily converted into octahedral complexes of d^6 electronic configuration by expansion of their coordination number upon adduct formation with a covalent molecule^{9,10}. A survey of the known oxidative addition reactions of d^8 complexes indicates that the tendency to form stable adducts of d^6 configuration increases as one goes from first to third row transition elements and from right to left within group VIII¹¹. As a part of our general investigations on palladium(II) and platinum(II) chelates with 8-quinolinols, it was considered worthwhile to study the oxidative addition reactions of these chelates. We have also carried out the reactions of palladium(II) and platinum(II) chelates of 8-quinolinol with anhydrous stannous chloride, in benzonitrile medium, in an attempt to isolate compounds of these complexes containing bivalent tin. The results of our studies are presented in this communication.

Experimental

K_2PtCl_4 and Na_2PdCl_4 were prepared by the reported methods¹². Anhydrous tin(II) chloride was prepared by dehydration of reagent grade tin(II) chloride dihydrate, $SnCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, by reaction with acetic anhydride¹³ and stored in a tightly closed ground glass bottle. Iodine monochloride and 5,7-disubstituted-8-quinolinols were prepared by the literature methods¹⁴⁻¹⁷. Solvents were purified and dried prior to use. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Model 221 spectrophotometer equipped with CsBr optics. The ultra-violet and visible spectra were recorded on a

Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer. The diffuse reflectance spectra of solid samples were obtained on Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer fitted with the standard reflectance attachment and employing a block of magnesium carbonate as standard.

1. *Bis*(8-quinolinolato)platinum(II) :

Hot solutions of K_2PtCl_4 (0.42 g, 0.001 mole) in water (20 ml) and 8-quinolinol (0.029 g, 0.002 mole) in alcohol (10-15 ml) were mixed together with stirring. The pH of the resulting mixture was adjusted to 6.0-6.5 with sodium hydroxide solution (2%) and heated on a water bath for 1-1½ hrs. The brown solid that separated out was collected on a filter, washed with hot water, dried and was recrystallised from chloroform. Yield, 0.3 g, (62%), m.p. decomp. >300°. Anal. Found: C, 44.62; H, 2.8; N, 5.2 Pt, 40.15%. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{12}N_2O_2Pt$; C, 44.72; H, 2.5; N, 5.79; Pt, 40.36%. The same compound was obtained as a bright orange solid¹⁸ when in the above procedure the pH of the mixture was adjusted to 10.0-10.5. The analytical (Found: C, 44.30; H, 2.72; Pt, 40.2%) and electronic spectral data for the compounds indicate that the difference in colour might arise due to the isomeric nature of the compounds.

5,7-Dichloro-, dibromo- and diiodo-8-quinolinol chelates with Pt(II) were synthesized by refluxing for 8 hrs together, solutions of K_2PtCl_4 and the appropriate ligand in dioxane+water mixture in 1 : 2 mole ratio. Deeply coloured products obtained were repeatedly digested with hot dioxane. Yield, 60-70%. Palladium(II) chelates with 8-quinolinol and its 5,7-dichloro-, dibromo- and diiodo derivatives were prepared by mixing together solutions of Na_2PdCl_4 in water (20 ml) and the appropriate ligand in solvent (dioxane or acetic

[†] NCL Communication No. 2535.

* Author to whom correspondence should be addressed.

acid, 50 ml) in 1 : 2 mole ratio and by adjusting the pH of the resulting mixture to 6.0-6.5, with sodium hydroxide solution (2%) and by heating on water bath for 30 min. The products were either repeatedly digested with solvents such as, dioxane, methylene chloride, acetone, alcohol or recrystallized twice from chloroform. Yield, ~80%.

2. *Bis(5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato)platinum(II)* : m.p. decomp. $>310^\circ$. Anal. Found : C, 34.49 ; H, 1.85 ; N, 4.2 ; Pt, 30.9%. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_8N_2O_2Cl_4Pt$: C, 34.8 ; H, 1.30 ; N, 4.51 ; Pt, 31.4%.

3. *Bis(5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinolato)platinum(II)* : m.p. decomp. $>300^\circ$. Anal. Found : C, 27.22 ; H, 1.30 ; N, 3.9 ; Pt, 24.02%. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_8N_2O_2Br_4Pt$: C, 27.06 ; H, 1.01 ; N, 3.51 ; Pt, 24.41%.

4. *Bis(5,7-diiodo-8-quinolinolato)platinum(II)* : decomp. 290° . Anal. Found : C, 22.3 ; H, 1.43 ; N, 3.4 ; Pt, 19.2%. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_8N_2O_2I_4Pt$: C, 21.9 ; H, 0.82 ; N, 2.83 ; Pt, 19.77%.

5. *Bis(8-quinolinolato)palladium(II)*¹⁰ : Anal. Found : C, 54.27 ; H, 3.3 ; N, 6.80 ; Pd, 26.6%. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{12}N_2O_2Pd$: C, 54.77 ; H, 3.06 ; N, 7.1 ; Pd, 27.04%.

6. *Bis(5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato)palladium(II)* : Anal. Found : C, 39.38 ; H, 2.2 ; N, 4.86 ; Pd, 20.39%. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_8N_2O_2Cl_4Pd$: C, 40.62 ; H, 1.5 ; N, 5.26 ; Pd, 19.98%.

7. *Bis(5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinolato)palladium(II)* : Anal. Found : C, 31.58 ; H, 1.85 ; N, 3.7 ; Pd, 15.23%. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_8N_2O_2Br_4Pd$: C, 30.44 ; H, 1.14 ; N, 3.94 ; Pd, 14.98%.

8. *Bis(5,7-diiodo-8-quinolinolato)palladium(II)* : decomp. 300° . Anal. Found : C, 24.91 ; H, 1.3 ; N, 2.8 ; Pd, 11.30%. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_8N_2O_2I_4Pd$: C, 24.07 ; H, 0.90 ; N, 3.12 ; Pd, 11.84%.

9. *Reactions of chlorine : Dichlorobis(5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato)platinum(IV)* : Chlorine was bubbled into a well-stirred suspension of *bis(8-quinolinolato)platinum(II)* (0.48 g ; 0.001 mole) in dry chloroform (120 ml) for 15-20 minutes. A dark reddish-brown solution was obtained. After an additional 10 minutes of stirring, the solution was filtered. The solvent was removed partially by evaporation at room temperature and the reddish-brown product obtained was dried under vacuum. Yield, 0.3 g (44.5%). Anal. Found : C, 30.38 ; H, 1.6 ; N, 3.97 ; Cl, 31.00 ; Pt, 28.3%. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_8N_2O_2Cl_6Pt$: C, 31.24 ; H, 1.16 ; N, 4.05 ; Cl, 30.73 ; Pt, 28.19%.

10. *Dichlorobis(5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato)-palladium(IV)* was prepared in a similar way. Yield ~33%. Decomp. 160° . Anal. Found : C, 34.8 ; H, 2.00 ; Cl, 34.98 ; Pd, 17.2%. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_8N_2O_2Cl_6Pd$: C, 35.83 ; H, 1.34 ; Cl, 35.25 ; Pd, 17.63%.

11. *Reactions of bromine : Dibromobis(5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinolato)platinum(IV)* : To a suspension of *bis(8-quinolinolato)platinum(II)*, (0.48 g ; 0.001 mole) in chloroform (50 ml), bromine (2 g) in chloroform (50 ml) was added dropwise with stirring at room temperature. The stirring was continued for 4 hrs. Reddish-brown solid obtained was collected on a filter, washed with chloroform (20-30 ml) and dried in vacuum. Yield, 0.50 g (52%). Decomp. $>300^\circ$. Anal. Found : C, 21.98 ; H, 1.45 ; N, 2.53 ; Br, 50.7 ; Pt, 19.89%. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_8N_2O_2Br_6Pt$: C, 22.55 ; H, 0.84 ; N, 2.92 ; Br, 50.0 ; Pt, 20.34%.

12. *Dibromobis(5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinolato)-palladium(IV)* was prepared in a similar way described above. Yield, 0.48 g (45%), m.p. 246° . Anal. Found : C, 20.41 ; H, 1.6 ; N, 2.54 ; Br, 61.0 ; Pd, 10.14%. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_8N_2O_2Br_6Pd$. $2HBr$: C, 20.95 ; H, 0.98 ; N, 2.71 ; Pd, 10.31 ; Br, 61.95%.

13. *Reactions of iodine monochloride : Dichlorobis(8-quinolinolato)platinum(IV)* : To a suspension of *bis(8-quinolinolato)platinum(II)*, (0.48 g, 0.001 mole) in chloroform (80 ml), maintained at $0-5^\circ$ was added with stirring a slight excess of ICl in acetic acid (0.81 g, in 50 ml). Stirring was continued at this temperature for 30 minutes first and later at room temperature for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hrs. It was filtered and the brown-solid obtained from the filtrate was further recrystallized from chloroform. Yield, 0.2 g (36%). Anal. Found : C, 39.41 ; H, 1.81 ; N, 4.8 ; Pt, 35.10%. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{12}N_2O_2Cl_2Pt$: C, 38.98 ; H, 2.18 ; N, 5.23 ; Pt, 35.19%.

14. *Reactions of $SnCl_2$: Bis(8-quinolinolato)-platinum(II)-tin(II) dichloride : Bis(8-quinolinolato)-platinum(II)*, (0.48 g, 0.001 mole) in benzonitrile (50 ml) and anhydrous tin(II) chloride (0.19 g, 0.001 mole) in benzonitrile (25 ml) were mixed together and refluxed for 3 hrs. The dark green solution was filtered on cooling to remove any suspended material and the solvent was removed partially under reduced pressure. The deep green solid that separated out on cooling was collected on a filter under suction and dried under vacuum. Yield, 0.56 g (72%), m.p. decomp. $>300^\circ$. Anal. Found : C, 3.82 ; H, 2.4 ; N, 4.8 ; Cl, 8.7%. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{12}N_2O_2Pt.SnCl_2.C_6H_5CN$: C, 35.64 ; H, 2.2 ; N, 5.41 ; Cl, 9.14%.

15. *Bis(8-quinolinolato)palladium(II) tin(II) chloride* was prepared in the same manner as above. Yield, 0.45 g (65%), m.p. decomp. > 300°. Anal. Found: C, 44.69; H, 2.8; N, 5.7; Cl, 9.9%. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{12}N_2O_2Pd.SnCl_2.C_6H_5CN$: C, 43.62; H, 2.49; N, 6.10; Cl, 10.31%.

Results and Discussion

The reactions of Pd(II) and Pt(II) chelates, *bis(8-quinolinolato)palladium(II)* and *bis(8-quinolinolato)platinum(II)*, with halogens (chlorine and bromine) proceed smoothly at room temperature to afford the oxidative addition products MOx_2X_2 [M = Pd(II) or Pt(II); X = Cl or Br] initially, which probably equilibrates to give, in addition, the disproportionate products MOx_2X and $MOxX_2$. The reaction may be schematically represented as follows:

Stable oxidative addition products of Pt(II) and Pd(II) chelates, MOx_2X_2 type only could be isolated. However, addition with stirring of methyl iodide at room temperature to a solution or suspension of *bis(8-quinolinolato)palladium(II)* or *platinum(II)* in $CHCl_3$ or acetonitrile and stirring for several hours, resulted in the recovery of the starting material only.

On addition of a slight excess of acetic acid solution of ICl, at room temperature to a solution of Pt(II) chelate in chloroform and stirring for 2 hrs, the corresponding dichloro *bis(8-quinolinolato)Pt(IV)* was obtained. The corresponding Pd(IV) compound could not be isolated. According to ionic hypothesis, iodine monochloride is partially ionized and chlorine oxidative addition reaction can take place by this mechanism or that iodine monochloride behaves towards certain metals very much like chlorine forming the metal chloride, some iodide, and free iodine²⁰ and further reactions of the metal chloride would result in the chlorinated product. Tauzher *et al.*^{21,22} have investigated the reactions between alkyl and aryl-*bis(dimethyl-glyoximate) cobalt(III)* and ICl in chloroform and observed that in the absence of excess of added chloride ion, the reactions proceed via electrophilic substitution mechanism, in presence of an excess of chloride ion, both oxidative dealkylation and radical attack can occur. The corresponding palladium(IV) complexes, however, could not be isolated.

Addition of anhydrous $SnCl_2$ to benzonitrile solution of *bis(8-quinolinolato)platinum(II)* or *palladium(II)*, refluxing for 3 hrs and subsequent removal of the solvent under reduced pressure yielded dark green air stable 1:1 complex.

Elemental analysis indicated that the products contain one mole of solvent of crystallization. Evings and Harrison have reported²³ recently lower isomer shift for platinum(II) and palladium(II) complexes containing bivalent tin ligands. [$PdCl_2.Sn(dbm)_2$ and $PtCl_2.Sn(dbm)_2$ Hdbm = dibenzoylmethane]. The isomer shifts indicate substantial removal of 5s electron density away from tin and/or increased shielding of the tin nucleus resulting from (d→p)π retrodonative bonding from palladium or platinum to tin.

The infrared spectra of Pt(IV) and Pd(IV) complexes isolated (by the addition of oxidants, Cl_2 , Br_2 , ICl) in the region 700 cm^{-1} – 300 cm^{-1} show bands assignable to Pt-halogen or Pd-halogen stretching vibrations which are absent in the spectra of 8-quinolinol or 5,7-dihalogeno-8-quinolinol chelates of Pt(II) and Pd(II). The bands present in the spectra of dichloro *bis(5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato)platinum(IV)* and dichloro-*bis(8-quinolinolato)platinum(IV)* at Ca. 346 cm^{-1} (m), and 336 cm^{-1} (m) and at Ca. 330 cm^{-1} (m) respectively are due to (Pt-Cl) vibrations^{24,25}. The position of the bands suggest addition of the oxidizing agent has been to the *trans*- or to the axial position in the complexes (i.e., not in the same plane as the 8-quinolinol). In tetrachloro(1,10-phenanthroline)platinum(IV) obtained by the oxidative addition of chlorine to dichloro(1,10-phenanthroline)platinum(II), *trans*-Cl absorptions are observed at Ca. 345 cm^{-1} . The band present at Ca. 365 cm^{-1} in the infrared spectrum was assigned to *cis*-Cl stretching vibration². Although (Pt-Br) vibrations in Pt(II) complexes with N-methyl imidazole²⁶ and in Pt(II) complex anions²⁴ are reported to occur at Ca. 220 cm^{-1} and at Ca. 205 cm^{-1} respectively, the medium intense band observed at Ca. 323 cm^{-1} in the spectra of dibromo-*bis(5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinolato)platinum(IV)* could arise due to Pt-Br. str. vibration. Hodges and Rund² have recently assigned the band observed at Ca. 325 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of tetrabromo(1,10-phenanthroline)platinum(IV) to (Pt-Br) vibration⁴. The band assignable to (Pd-Cl)⁷ is observed, in the spectrum of $Pd(5,7-Cl_2Ox)_2Cl_2$ at 330 cm^{-1} (m) on the basis of previous assignments.

In the spectra of Pt(II) and Pd(II) complex with 8-quinolinol containing bivalent tin, a structured broad medium intense band is observed in the region 330 cm^{-1} – 300 cm^{-1} . The Sn-Cl symmetric and antisymmetric stretching modes of $SnCl_2$ observed in the spectrum at Ca. 350 cm^{-1} and at 330 cm^{-1} respectively, on complex formation shift slightly to lower frequencies²⁰. The magnitude of the shift is of the order of $\sim 7\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The band at 322 cm^{-1} may be attributed to anti-symmetric Sn-Cl str. vibration²⁷. The symmetric Sn-Cl str. vibration apparently is masked due to the presence of other vibrations.

In the electronic absorption spectra of Pt(II) and Pd(II) chelates one should expect three spin allowed and three spin forbidden bands. The weaker bands at 18,500 cm^{-1} in $\text{Pt}(\text{OX})_2$ (red colour) and at 19,000 cm^{-1} in $\text{Pt}(\text{OX})_2$ (brown colour) and in *bis*(dichloro-8-quinolinolato) Pt(II) are assigned to spin-forbidden $d-d$ transitions, 3E_g and ${}^3A_{2g}$ excited states respectively^{28,29}. The first spin-allowed $d \rightarrow d$ transition, $b_{2g}(xy) \rightarrow b_{1g}(x^2-y^2)$ (${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$) is believed to occur at 25,000 cm^{-1} in PtCl_2^{2-} and about 43,000 cm^{-1} ⁴⁰ in $\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_4^{2+}$ complexes. The very intense absorption observed in the spectra at Ca. 36,000 cm^{-1} is perhaps due to $L \rightarrow M$ charge transfer process. In square planar dithiooxalato complexes of Pt(II), Pd(II) and Au(III), very intense $L \rightarrow M$ bands were observed at 36,400 cm^{-1} , 45,000 cm^{-1} and at 36,500 cm^{-1} respectively¹¹.

The ground state for d^6 Pt(IV) is ${}^1A_{1g}$. The ligand field transition $e_g t_{2g}^5 \leftarrow t_{2g}^6$ gives ${}^3T_{1g}$, ${}^3T_{2g}$ and ${}^1T_{1g}$ and ${}^1T_{2g}$ as excited states in increasing order of energy. The electronic spectra of Pt(IV) complexes show absorption bands at 20,000 cm^{-1} , 23,500 cm^{-1} and at 29,900 cm^{-1} . The bands at 20,000 cm^{-1} in Pt(IV) complexes are due to $d \rightarrow d$ transitions assigned^{30,31} to the singlet-triplet transition ${}^3T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^1A_{1g}$. The X-ray crystal structure for *bis*(8-quinolinolato)palladium(II) is reported³². The palladium coordination is square planar with Pd-N and Pd-O bond lengths of 2.02 Å. The absorption spectra of Pd(II) chelates with 8-quinolinols are similar to those of Pt(II) chelates. The lower energy band at 19,000 cm^{-1} is assigned to the spin-allowed $d \rightarrow d$ (${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$) transition. This is in agreement with the assignment reported for Pd(II) complexes³¹. The spin forbidden transitions, (weak bands) are reported to occur at 16,300 cm^{-1} and at 14,600 cm^{-1} in square planar halide complexes of palladium(II)³³ and are not observed in the spectra of Pd(II) chelates with 8-quinolinols and its 5,7-halogeno-substituted derivatives. In the case of Pd(II) chelates the $M \rightarrow L$ (π^*) band is probably covered by the very intense $L \rightarrow M$ band at $\sim 36,000$ cm^{-1} .

The bands (large values of ϵ) at 22,500 cm^{-1} , 29,500 cm^{-1} and the very intense bands at 36,000 cm^{-1} are interpreted respectively as $L(\pi) \rightarrow$ and $L(\sigma) \rightarrow M$ charge transition bands^{32,34}. The absorption spectra of Pd(II) and Pt(II) chelates with 8-quinolinols do not show any absorptions in the near infrared region. The diffuse reflectance spectra of the chelates of Pt(II) with 5,7-dibromo- and 5,7-diiodo-8-quinolinol were recorded and the spectra also do not show any absorptions in this region. From the similarity in the spectral characteristics with reported square planar complexes^{32,34}, it may be inferred that Pt(II) and Pd(II) chelates with 8-quinolinols studied here possess square planar geometry.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. D. N. Sen, Senior Scientist, Inorganic Chemistry Division, N.C.L., Poona for his keen interest and for helpful discussions.

References

1. J. P. COLLMAN and C. T. SEARS, Jr., *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 7, 27.
2. K. I. HODGES and J. V. RUND, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1975, 14, 525.
3. M. E. KRAMER and J. L. BURMEISTER, *Syn. React. Inorg. Metal. Org. Chem.*, 1977, 7, 69.
4. R. USÓN, J. FORNIÉS, P. ESPINET and J. GARIN, *Syn. React. Inorg. Metal. Org. Chem.*, 1977, 7, 211.
5. A. PRLOSO, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton*, 1978, 699.
6. T. V. ASHWORTH, J. E. SINGLETON, D. J. A. de WAAL, W. J. LOUW, E. SINGLETON and E. VAN DER STOK, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton*, 1978, 340.
7. R. USÓN, J. FORNIÉS and R. NAVARRO, *Syn. React. Inorg. Metal. Org. Chem.*, 1977, 7, 235.
8. J. HALPERN, *Accts. Chem. Res.*, 1970, 3, 386.
9. J. P. COLLMAN and W. R. ROPER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 88, 3504 and references therein.
10. J. P. COLLMAN and W. R. ROPER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 87, 4008.
11. R. S. NYHOLM and K. VRIEZE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 5337.
12. G. BRAUER, "Handbook of Preparative Inorganic Chemistry", Academic Press, New York, Vol. II, 2nd Edn., p. 1572 and 1584, (1965).
13. G. BRAUER, "Handbook of Preparative Inorganic Chemistry", Academic Press, Vol. I, 2nd Edn., 728, 1963.
- 14a. A. I. VOGEL, *Elementary Practical Organic Chemistry*, Longmans Green & Co., London, 3rd Edn., 767, (1958).
- 14b. G. BRAUER "Handbook of Preparative Inorganic Chemistry", Academic Press, New York, Vol. I, 2nd Edn., 290, (1963).
15. L. W. HASSE, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1929, 78, 113.
16. TAMAS NORGRADI, *Chem. Ber.*, 1952, 85, 104.
17. T. N. GHOSH, S. L. LASKAR and S. BANERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 352.
18. R. BALLARDINI, M. T. INDELLI, G. VARANI, C. A. BIGNOZZI and F. SCANDOLA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1978, 31, L, 423.
19. A. S. BAILEY, R. J. P. WILLIAMS and J. D. WRIGHT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 2579.
20. J. W. MELLOR "A Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", Longmans Green & Co., London, Vol. II, 116, (1937).
21. R. DREOS, G. TAUZHER, N. MARSICH and G. COSTA, *J. Organometal Chem.*, 1975, 92, 227.
22. R. DREOS, G. TAUZHER, N. MARSICH and G. COSTA, *J. Organometal Chem.*, 1976, 108, 235.
23. P. F. R. EVINGS and P. G. HARRISON, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1978, 28, L, 167.
24. P. J. HENDRA, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1967, 1298.
25. C. G. VAN KRALINGEN and J. REEDIJK, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1978, 30, 171.
26. D. TRVAULT and K. NAKAMOTO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, 15, 1282.

27. (Miss) S. N. BHIDE, P. UMAPATHY and D. N. SEN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 851.
28. D. S. MARTIN, M. A. TICKER and A. J. KASSMAN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 1682.
29. H. BASCH and H. B. GRAY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 365.
30. C. K. JÖRGENSEN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1962, **24**, 1571.
31. P. C. SRIVASTAVA and B. K. BANERJEE, *Acta. Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1978, **96**, 259.
32. C. K. PROUT and A. G. WHEELER, *J. Chem. Soc., A*, 1966, 1286.
33. W. R. MASON, III and H. B. GRAY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 5721.
34. A. R. LATHAM, V. C. HASCALL and H. B. GRAY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 788.